

ANALYSIS OF QUALITY PRACTICES IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED INDUSTRIES USING STATISTICAL TOOLS: CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In the era of globalization and privatization, businesses must adapt to current market challenges, and one effective approach is the application of Total Quality Management (TQM) principles. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in generating employment and strengthening the economy of developing countries like India. To achieve customer satisfaction, the quality of products produced by SMEs is essential. Key factors for quality improvement include enhancing customer satisfaction, increasing profits, and minimizing losses. These goals can be achieved through the adoption of advanced quality philosophies and TQM principles. This paper explores the identification of critical success factors that influence the effectiveness of quality practices in SMEs. The study aims to establish guidelines for management to improve firm productivity. It includes a questionnaire survey to assess the implementation of TQM practices within the governance structures of SMEs. Based on the data collected, critical factors are prioritized. The study formulates three hypotheses: employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and operational effectiveness. Statistical analysis is conducted using T-tests, one-way ANOVA, and MANOVA to test the hypotheses. The findings suggest that SMEs implementing TQM are more effective in meeting the needs of employees, customers, and operational goals.

Keywords: Hypothesis, MANOVA Test, One-way ANOVA, SME's, TQM, T-test, Quality

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1. INTRODUCTION

The economic development of a nation is intrinsically linked to the growth of its industrial sector. The expansion of this sector drives greater utilization of natural resources, enhances the production of goods and services, generates employment opportunities, and elevates the overall standard of living. Since India's independence, efforts have been made to strengthen the industrial base of the country, with both large-scale industries and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contributing significantly to this goal. In particular, SME's play a pivotal role in promoting socio-economic development and achieving equitable growth. Over the decades, the concept of Total Quality Management (TQM) has become central to management practices across industries, regardless of their size or type. TQM is based on fundamental principles such as consumer focus, continuous improvement, and effective human resource management, which are essential for the successful implementation of quality practices across industries, including small, medium, and large-scale enterprises [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. TQM is a comprehensive approach that requires businesses to adopt new management practices and cultivate a culture of quality that impacts every aspect of the organization, including processes, employees, and the allocation of organizational resources [8, 9, 10]. Customer satisfaction remains one of the most critical factors for the success of any organization, as the growth of a business is directly tied to the ability to meet customer expectations. To achieve total customer satisfaction in terms of product quality, delivery, and after-sales service, organizations, particularly small-scale industries, have no alternative but to adopt TQM principles in a holistic manner. Extensive research has been conducted across various industries to examine the implementation of quality practices using TQM. Management awareness of the importance of TQM, including business process re-engineering and other continuous improvement techniques, has been studied through benchmarking efforts aimed at identifying best practices [11]. Studies on TQM principles and practices across both service and manufacturing sectors suggest that there is little significant difference in the adoption of TQM practices and quality performance between the two sectors [12]. Recent research on business performance improvement has also highlighted the positive impact of TQM on organizational outcomes [13]. This empirical research investigates the correlation between TQM practices and business performance, demonstrating how TQM influences different levels of performance. Further simulations have conceptualized TQM around core principles such as customer focus, continuous improvement, and human resource management [14]. The necessary resources for production and the associated productivity measures have also been discussed in the context of TQM practices [15]. TQM, as a management technique, is widely adopted in manufacturing organizations to enhance product quality while minimizing costs through continuous improvement practices [16]. Recognized as a strategic, tactical, and operational tool, TQM has become a central theme in quality management research [17]. Computational analyses, such as t-tests and MANOVA, have been used to evaluate the implementation of TQM practices in 222 manufacturing and service companies, revealing significant variations in TQM adoption based on company size, industry type, and innovation levels [18]. While TQM is predominantly associated with manufacturing, its application in other sectors, including construction, has been explored [19]. Achieving customer satisfaction is a core principle of TQM, which is crucial for organizations across all industries, including construction, as they face increasing global competition and the demand for higher quality products and services [20]. TQM practices, critical success factors, and barriers to implementation, along with their impact on business outcomes, have been analyzed using statistical methods such as t-tests and ANOVA in the context of the electric fan manufacturing industry in Pakistan [21]. Descriptive statistical techniques, including measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion, have been employed to analyze TQM practices [22]. Inferential statistics, including Pearson correlation, hypothesis testing, analysis of variance (ANOVA), stepwise regression, one-sample t-test, F-

test, chi-square tests, and significance levels, have been utilized to assess the implementation of quality practices in both manufacturing and service industries in Riyadh city. The objective of this paper is to investigate the implementation of quality principles in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in and around Bellary city, through the application of statistical analyses.

2. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework for implementing quality practices in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) involves three key components: data collection methods, population and sample size, and data analysis techniques. Potential issues arising from respondents' difficulties in understanding the questions across the industries surveyed were addressed through a pilot study. The questionnaire was carefully designed to ensure it was sensitive to the respondents' emotions, while also considering other relevant factors. The final version of the questionnaire was developed after several iterations, including reformatting and continuous refinements. Data were collected via surveys, which included questionnaires focused on industry characteristics, employee and customer satisfaction, and the effectiveness of quality practices. In the case of employee and customer satisfaction, a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 was employed to gauge responses.

Table 1 List of factors considered in the formulation of questionnaire.

The survey was conducted across various small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in different regions of Bellary city, taking into account all relevant factors influencing Total Quality Management (TQM). A total of 71 SMEs (comprising 40 small and 31 medium-sized enterprises) voluntarily participated in the survey, providing valuable insights for the implementation of TQM principles. The survey covered a range of sectors, including steel, agro-food, cotton, garments, and MRF tyres and treads, located in and around Bellary city. The questionnaire was designed to collect data on personnel, organizational characteristics, and

factors influencing quality management practices in SMEs. A detailed list of the personnel, organizational, and other influencing factors considered in the design of the questionnaire is presented in Table 1.

2.1 Formulating the Research Hypotheses

The data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed using various statistical tests, including hypothesis testing, significance testing, and descriptive statistics. The differences in the means between two categories of SMEs were examined through hypothesis testing, utilizing SPSS software. Initially, three primary hypotheses were formulated and tested to understand how the selected sample would respond to the questions posed in the questionnaire.

Fig. 1 Dissertation Model (Researchers, 2008).

Fig. 1 illustrates the hypotheses developed from the dissertation model, which is divided into three components: employee satisfaction, operational effectiveness, and customer satisfaction. Hypothesis 1 posits that employee satisfaction is higher in TQM-oriented SMEs compared to non-TQM SMEs. It is hypothesized that quality improvement initiatives are more successful when supported by a committed and skilled workforce. Such initiatives are further enhanced by

rewards, recognition, the sponsorship of higher education, and employee training, all of which contribute to the quality-driven culture. This, in turn, encourages employees to take greater responsibility, communicate more effectively, and demonstrate creativity and innovation. Hypothesis 2 suggests that customer satisfaction is higher in TQM-based SMEs compared to non-TQM SMEs, as illustrated in Fig. 1, following the findings of Jordan (2002). Companies implementing TQM are more responsive to customer needs and are quicker to address them. Total Quality Management (TQM) emphasizes customer focus, as depicted in Fig.1, to enhance the quality of services provided to consumers by addressing their needs and resolving their issues. SMEs must be attuned to customer requirements and assess how well their managerial performance aligns with these needs, while maintaining a satisfactory level of customer satisfaction. According to Muffatto and Panizzolo (1995), customer requirements are met by delivering products or services on time and of the required quality. Hypothesis 3 posits that operational performance is superior in TQM-oriented SMEs compared to non-TQM SMEs in the context of small and medium-sized enterprises. The adoption of TQM is expected to lead to improved organizational performance. Sila (2007) demonstrated that supplier involvement in the quality improvement process plays a significant role in enhancing operational effectiveness. Furthermore, continuous improvement, a core principle of TQM, contributes to the optimization of operational efficiency."

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides a detailed analysis of the data obtained through a questionnaire survey. The analysis includes various statistical tests, namely descriptive statistics, independent samples t-test, one-way ANOVA, and MANOVA, applied to data collected from small and medium-scale industries. Key statistical measures, such as mean, standard deviation, and mean performance based on mean differences, were calculated for employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, and operational effectiveness. Initially, the p-value is used to assess the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis, as defined by Fisher. A p-value less than 0.01 indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, leading to its rejection. A p-value between 0.01 and 0.05 suggests moderate evidence against the null hypothesis, warranting its rejection. P-values between 0.05 and 0.10 provide weak evidence against the null hypothesis and are generally insufficient to reject it. Higher p-values indicate even weaker evidence for rejecting the null hypothesis. Ultimately, the results of the t-test, one-way ANOVA, and MANOVA, performed using SPSS software, provide a comprehensive conclusion regarding the research questions.

3.1 EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION

3.1.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the customer satisfaction variables across a sample of 71 small and medium-scale industries. The analysis compares the descriptive statistics for six numerical variables.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics for customer satisfaction

Descriptive Statistics (Sample-71)					
S. No.	Factors	Type of industry	Mean	Std.	SE of mean
		Small/ Medium		Deviation	
CS1	The standard quality in service	small	3.225	0.8912	0.11
		medium	3.7097	0.78288	0.09
		Total	3.4366	0.87395	0.1
CS2	Listen to customer complains	small	2.575	0.98417	0.12
		medium	3.8387	0.82044	0.1
		Total	3.1268	1.1075	0.13
CS3	Repeat of customer	small	2.8	1.09075	0.13
		medium	3.6774	0.79108	0.09
		Total	3.1831	1.05978	0.13
CS4	Product recommendation by customer	small	2.9	0.87119	0.1
		medium	3.7097	0.78288	0.09
		Total	3.2535	0.92146	0.11
CS5	Quick response to customer	small	2.975	0.76753	0.09
		medium	3.7742	0.762	0.09
		Total	3.3239	0.85815	0.1
CS6	Company giving warrantee to customer	small	2.25	1.35401	0.16
		medium	3.8387	0.89803	0.11
		Total	2.9437	1.41307	0.17

The highest mean value, 3.4366, was recorded for "standard quality in service," while the lowest mean, 2.9437, was found for "company offering warranty to customers." Most of the means for the numerical variables are above 3, with the exception of the warranty offering. This may indicate that customers are dissatisfied with the warranty period provided for the products. Furthermore, the standard deviation for "quick response to customer" is lower compared to other variables related to customer satisfaction, suggesting that customers generally perceive a consistent level of satisfaction with the responsiveness of the small and medium-scale enterprises, in contrast to the other defined variables. Table 3 provides the descriptive statistics for the employee satisfaction variables across the same sample of 71 small and medium-scale industries. The highest mean value, 3.5321, was observed for "individual effort," while the lowest mean value, 3.1127, was recorded for "continuous improvement." The mean for most of the variables is above 3.2, except for "individual effort." This could reflect a lack of recognition for employees' individual contributions.

Table 3 Descriptive statistics for employee satisfaction

Descriptive Statistics (Sample-71)					
S. No	Factors	Type of industry Small/Medium	Mean	Std. Deviation	SE of Mean
ES1	Satisfaction with authority	small	2.9744	0.95936	0.11
		medium	3.6562	0.86544	0.10
		Total	3.2817	0.97370	0.12
ES2	Training for workers	small	2.7179	0.94448	0.11
		medium	3.7813	0.79248	0.09
		Total	3.1972	1.02288	0.12
ES3	Encouragement of team effort	small	2.9487	0.91619	0.11
		medium	3.5938	0.83702	0.10
		Total	3.2394	0.93296	0.11
ES4	Continuous improvement	small	2.7179	0.91619	0.11
		medium	3.5938	0.97912	0.12
		Total	3.1127	1.03578	0.12
ES5	Management recognizes individual effort	small	2.9487	0.94448	0.11
		medium	3.5625	0.91361	0.11
		Total	3.2254	0.97390	0.12
ES6	Mistakes made while responding to customer	small	3.0000	0.91766	0.11
		medium	3.6250	0.83280	0.10
		Total	3.2817	0.92864	0.11
ES7	Flexibility of job	small	2.8974	1.07103	0.13
		medium	3.7188	0.88843	0.11
		Total	3.2676	1.06848	0.13
ES8	Employee involvement in decision making	small	2.7949	1.05580	0.13
		medium	3.7500	0.76200	0.09
		Total	3.2254	1.04468	0.12
ES9	Individual effort is recognized in delivering quality service	small	2.7179	0.97194	0.12
		medium	3.6563	0.70066	0.08
		Total	3.1408	0.97535	0.12
ES10	Individual effort	small	3.0256	0.93153	0.11
		medium	3.7500	0.84242	0.10
		Total	3.3521	0.95765	0.11

3.1.2 T-Test

Table 4 presents the results of a T-test conducted on the customer satisfaction parameters. It was found that the assumption of homogeneity of variances was violated, although the impact of this violation on the validity of the T-test results was considered in the analysis. For the parameter of warranty provision by the company, the significance value was found to be less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference, and no violation of the equality of variances assumption was observed. In contrast, for all other parameters, the significance values exceeded 0.05, suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances. However, it is important to note that the SPSS software automatically adjusts for such violations in the test. Additionally, the results indicate a significant difference between small and medium-scale enterprises, with a 99% confidence level ($p < 0.01$), confirming the presence of a substantial difference between the groups based on the chosen sample.

Table 5 summarizes the T-test results for the employee satisfaction parameters. All significance values were found to be less than 0.05, indicating statistically significant differences for all defined numerical variables, with no violations of the homogeneity of variances assumption.

Table 6 presents the results of the T-test for the operational effectiveness parameters of the organization. In this case, the significance values for all parameters exceeded 0.05, suggesting a violation of the assumption of equal variances.

Table 4 T-test for customer satisfaction

		Test Value=0.05					
S. No.	Factors	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
CS1	Standard quality in service	-2.395	69	.019	-.48468	.20239	-.88844
CS2	Listen to customer complains	-5.762	69	.000	-1.26371	.21933	-1.70125
CS3	Repeat of customer	-3.773	69	.000	-.87742	.23256	-1.34136
CS4	Product recommendation by customer	-4.057	69	.000	-.80968	.19955	-1.20777
CS5	Quick response to customer	-4.365	69	.000	-.79919	.18309	-1.16444
CS6	Company giving warranteeto customer	-5.638	69	.000	-1.58871	.28180	-2.15088

Table 5 T-test for employee satisfaction

		Test Value=0.05					
S. No.	Factors	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
ES1	Satisfaction with authority	-3.113	69	.003	-.68189	-1.11887	-.24491
ES2	Training for workers	-5.069	69	.000	-	-1.48177	-.64483
ES3	Encouragement of team effort	-3.068	69	.003	1.0633 -.64503	-1.06448	-.22559
ES4	Continuous improvement	-3.886	69	.000	-.87580	-1.32545	-.42615
ES5	Management recognizes individual effort	-2.765	69	.007	-.61378	-1.05665	-.17091
ES6	Mistakes made while responding to customer	-3.068	69	.003	-.64503	-1.06448	-.22559
ES7	Flexibility of job	-3.467	69	.001	-.82131	-1.29389	-.34874
ES8	Employee involvement in decision making	-4.281	69	.000	-.95513	-1.40017	-.51009
ES9	Individual effort is recognized in delivering quality service	-4.571	69	.000	-.93830	-1.34785	-.52875
ES10	Individual effort	-3.467	69	.001	-.82131	-1.29389	-.34874

Table 6 T-test for operational effectiveness

S. No.	Factors	Test			Value=0.05		
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
OE1	Is your company ISO certified	-.140	69	.889	-.00561	-.08546	.07424
OE2	Have you heard of TQM	-.532	69	.596	-.06410	-.30435	.17614
OE3	Does the organization apply TQM	-2.920	69	.005	-.38542	-.64877	-.12207
OE4	Does the organization apply SQP	1.192	69	.237	.14103	-.09498	.37703
OE5	Use of consultant during ISO/TQM	-.532	69	.596	-.06410	-.30435	.17614
OE6	Overall, do you think TQM brings positive effects	-.140	69	.889	-.00561	-.08546	.07424
OE7	Focus on continuous improvement of product	1.192	69	.237	.14103	-.09498	.37703
OE8	Focus on continuous improvement of process	-.532	69	.596	-.06410	-.30435	.17614

3.1.3 One Way ANOVA Test

Table 7 presents the results of a one-way between-groups Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) conducted to examine the impact of various customer satisfaction parameters. Respondents were grouped based on their level of knowledge of Total Quality Management (TQM). The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference in the parameter related to "standard quality in service" ($p = 0.019$). However, for all other customer satisfaction parameters, the significance values were found to be non-significant, with p-values of zero, indicating no differences between groups.

Table 8 displays the ANOVA results for employee satisfaction. A significant difference was observed in the parameter "Management recognizes individual effort," with the highest statistical significance ($p = 0.007$), suggesting a meaningful variance between groups in relation to this factor.

Table 9 presents the ANOVA results for operational effectiveness within the organization. It was found that the parameter related to ISO certification exhibited a very high p-value of 0.889, indicating no statistically significant difference across the groups of visited SMEs regarding their ISO certification status.

Table 7 ANOVA-test results for customer satisfaction

ANOVA					
The standard quality in service					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.103	1	4.103	5.735	.019
Within Groups	49.362	69	.715		
Total	53.465	70			
Listen to customer complains					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	27.891	1	27.891	33.198	.000
Within Groups	57.969	69	.840		
Total	85.859	70			
Repeat of customer					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.446	1	13.446	14.235	.000
Within Groups	65.174	69	.945		
Total	78.620	70			
Product recommendation by customer					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.450	1	11.450	16.463	.000
Within Groups	47.987	69	.695		
Total	59.437	70			
Quick response to customer					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.155	1	11.155	19.054	.000
Within Groups	40.394	69	.585		
Total	51.549	70			
Company giving warrantee to customer					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	44.081	1	44.081	31.785	.000
Within Groups	95.694	69	1.387		
Total	139.775	70			

Table 8 ANOVA-test results for employee satisfaction

ANOVA					
Satisfaction with authority					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8.173	1	8.173	9.691	.003
Within Groups	58.193	69	.843		
Total	66.366	70			
Training for workers					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19.873	1	19.873	25.695	.000
Within Groups	53.366	69	.773		
Total	73.239	70			
Encouragement of team effort					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.313	1	7.313	9.412	.003
Within Groups	53.616	69	.777		
Total	60.930	70			
Continuous improvement					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.482	1	13.482	15.098	.000
Within Groups	61.616	69	.893		
Total	75.099	70			
Management recognizes the individual effort					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6.622	1	6.622	7.644	.007
Within Groups	59.772	69	.866		
Total	66.394	70			
Mistakes made while responding to customer					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6.866	1	6.866	8.855	.004
Within Groups	53.500	69	.775		
Total	60.366	70			
Flexibility of job					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.857	1	11.857	12.021	.001
Within Groups	68.058	69	.986		
Total	79.915	70			
employee involvement in decision making					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	16.035	1	16.035	18.331	.000
Within Groups	60.359	69	.875		
Total	76.394	70			
Individual effort is recognized in delivering quality service					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	15.475	1	15.475	20.890	.000
Within Groups	51.116	69	.741		
Total	66.592	70			
Individual effort					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.

Between Groups	9.223	1	9.223	11.576	.001
Within Groups	54.974	69	.797		
Total	64.197	70			

Table 9 ANOVA-test results for operational effectiveness

ANOVA					
Is your company ISO certified					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.001	1	.001	.020	.889
Within Groups	1.943	69	.028		
Total	1.944	70			
Have you heard of TQM					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.	.
Within Groups	.000	69	.000		
Total	.000	70			
Does the organization apply TQM					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.611	1	2.611	8.524	.005
Within Groups	21.135	69	.306		
Total	23.746	70			
Does the organization apply SQP					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.350	1	.350	1.421	.237
Within Groups	16.974	69	.246		
Total	17.324	70			
Use of consultant during ISO/TQM					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.072	1	.072	.283	.596
Within Groups	17.590	69	.255		
Total	17.662	70			
Overall do you think TQM brings positive effects					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.	.
Within Groups	.000	69	.000		
Total	.000	70			
Focus on continuous improvement of product					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.	.
Within Groups	.000	69	.000		
Total	.000	70			
Focus on continuous improvement of process					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.	.
Within Groups	.000	69	.000		
Total	.000	70			

3.1.4 MANOVA Test

Table 10 presents the results of a one-way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) conducted to assess customer satisfaction as it relates to quality practices in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The statistical significance of the one-way MANOVA is indicated in the second row of Table 10, where the p-value is reported as 0.000, which is less than the 0.05

threshold for significance. This result suggests a statistically significant difference between small and medium-scale enterprises in terms of customer satisfaction and quality practices. Table 11 provides the results of a one-way MANOVA for employee satisfaction. The p-value for this analysis is also 0.000, which is less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference between small and medium-scale enterprises in employee satisfaction.

Table 12 shows the results of a one-way MANOVA for operational effectiveness within the organization. Similarly, the p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, demonstrating a statistically significant difference between small and medium-scale enterprises in terms of operational effectiveness.

Table 10. MANOVA-test results for customer satisfaction

Multivariate Tests^a									
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Paramete	Observed Power ^c
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	0.968	322.967 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.968	1937.805	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	0.032	322.967 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.968	1937.805	1.000
	Hotelling's	30.278	322.967 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.968	1937.805	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	30.278	322.967 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.968	1937.805	1.000
Customer satisfaction	Pillai's Trace	0.398	7.055 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.398	42.328	.999
	Wilks' Lambda	0.602	7.055 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.398	42.328	.999
	Hotelling's	0.661	7.055 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.398	42.328	.999
	Roy's Largest	0.661	7.055 ^b	6.000	64.000	.000	.398	42.328	.999

a. Design: Intercept + Type of industry
b. Exact statistic
c. Computed using alpha = .05

Table 11. MANOVA-test results for employee satisfaction

Multivariate Tests^a									
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Paramete	Observed Power ^c
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.963	157.209 ^b	10.000	60.000	.000	.963	1572.087	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.037	157.209 ^b	10.000	60.000	.000	.963	1572.087	1.000
	Hotelling's	26.201	157.209 ^b	10.000	60.000	.000	.963	1572.087	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	26.201	157.209 ^b	10.000	60.000	.000	.963	1572.087	1.000
Employee Satisfaction	Pillai's Trace	.351	3.242 ^b	10.000	60.000	.002	.351	32.425	.975
	Wilks' Lambda	.649	3.242 ^b	10.000	60.000	.002	.351	32.425	.975
	Hotelling's	.540	3.242 ^b	10.000	60.000	.002	.351	32.425	.975
	Roy's Largest	.540	3.242 ^b	10.000	60.000	.002	.351	32.425	.975

a. Design: Intercept + Type of industry
b. Exact statistic
c. Computed using alpha = .05

Table 12. MANOVA-test results for operational effectiveness

Multivariate Tests ^a									
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Paramete	Observed Power ^c
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.983	962.244 ^b	4.000	66.000	.000	.983	962.244 ^b	4.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.017	962.244 ^b	4.000	66.000	.000	.017	962.244 ^b	4.000
	Hotelling's	58.318	962.244 ^b	4.000	66.000	.000	58.318	962.244 ^b	4.000
	Roy's Largest Root	58.318	962.244 ^b	4.000	66.000	.000	58.318	962.244 ^b	4.000
Operational effectiveness	Pillai's Trace	.118	2.215 ^b	4.000	66.000	.077	.118	2.215 ^b	4.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.882	2.215 ^b	4.000	66.000	.077	.882	2.215 ^b	4.000
	Hotelling's	.134	2.215 ^b	4.000	66.000	.077	.134	2.215 ^b	4.000
	Roy's Largest	.134	2.215 ^b	4.000	66.000	.077	.134	2.215 ^b	4.000

a. Design: Intercept + Type of industry
 b. Exact statistic
 c. Computed using alpha = .05

4. CONCLUSION

The present study identifies and analyzes the critical factors influencing the implementation of quality practices in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Statistical analysis reveals that these critical factors play a significant role in enhancing the performance and sustainability of Total Quality Management (TQM) in SMEs. Specifically, the implementation of TQM was found to improve both quality and cost efficiency across service and production processes, resulting in increased productivity, faster job completion, and reduced product rejection rates. Key input factors such as product quality, quality policy, management commitment, planning, resource management, purchasing, and measurement analysis were identified as drivers of performance in various output parameters. These output parameters include employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, product realization, quality outcomes, and environmental performance, all of which contribute to the overall improvement of the quality management system within SMEs. Furthermore, the analysis indicates that the greatest statistically significant differences were observed in the areas of operational effectiveness and customer satisfaction, with these factors showing a more pronounced impact compared to employee satisfaction. This suggests that TQM implementation has a stronger effect on operational and customer-related outcomes than on employee satisfaction in the studied SMEs.

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